

Learning Evaluation Management: Improving The Quality of Graduates in State Islamic Institute of Palopo

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ABSTRACT

This research aimed to evaluate the application of learning evaluation management to improve academic output at the Palopo State Islamic Institute. The work is qualitatively analytical, with pedagogical, ethical, and sociological methods. Research items were research implementers and graduates, and instructions for assessment, interview instruction, and reporting were the resources used. Results showed that practising assessment management consists of planning, organizing, implementing, and evaluating systems. At the planning stage, schedules learning assessment maintains the timetable by referring to the academic calendar, and arranges a location for lectures, while at the evaluation stage, UTS and UAS are done by a professor who teaches the subject. Management of learning evaluation constraints include; incomplete several teaching materials to affect planning; also, some students who did not receive a result in the previous semester (comprehensive examination) are late in entering test questions in the organizational aspect. Facilities factors have less impact on assessing research. Implementation challenges include student planning, test deception, and the lack of a set time to review the curriculum.

INTRODUCTION

The objective of the Education Quality Improvement Program is to achieve substantive national educational goals manifested in the full competence of students, including academic competence or intellectual capital, social competence or social capital, moral competence or moral capital; (Miftahurrohman, 2014: 197) and through improving the quality of learning and the quality of the assessment system (Djamari, 2003: 12). Increasing the quality of learning at different educational levels will improve the quality of education. Efforts to improve the quality of education will work well if supported by the competence and willingness of educational managers to improve continuously (Nurdin, 2020). Systematic management of education in the realm of the teaching and learning process is an essential requirement in achieving the desired educational goals (Ilham, 2020: 16). Thus, ongoing educational innovation in the educational program process, including learning evaluation, is a requirement to be implemented immediately.

The learning process is one of the critical factors for achieving educational goals, while the evaluation factor for both process and learning outcomes is a critical factor for learning efficiency. A practical assessment system encourages lecturers to identify the right teaching strategies and inspire students to learn more (Djamari, 2000). Assessment, of course, must be carried out continuously and continuously and requires recording of progress levels as feedback for lecturers to evaluate learning activities (Firman, 2014: 42). Therefore, an understanding of the evaluation system is needed to assess

the desired goal. Evaluation in the education sector is macro, and some are micro. Micro-oriented evaluation is educational programs, namely programs designed to improve the education sector, whereas micro-evaluations are often used at class level primarily to determine students' learning achievements (Djamari, 2000). This learning achievement is not only cognitive, but also includes all the potential that exists in students so that the micro-evaluation target is the learning program in the classroom, and the person in charge is the teacher for schools or university lecturers.

Optimize resource utilization and coordinate tasks to achieve goals through management. Management functions as planning, organization (G.R. Terry; Farhani, 2019), leading (Daft; Nuraeni, 2016), motivating (John F. Mee; Randi 2016), controlling, and coordinating (Henri Fayol; Zaini, 2015). In line with this, as a manager in a class organization, as a manager, educators' activities include planning, organizing, leading, and evaluating the results of the teaching and learning activities they manage. These management functions have in common that each manager must perform sequentially to implement the management process correctly. (Hasibuan, 2001: 3-4). Therefore, educators need to understand the management of education carefully in an institution in order to achieve the expected goals.

Tertiary institutions conduct a formal learning assessment to produce not only intellectually good but also noble and responsible experts in their field of expertise. Based on the 2003 National Education System Law No. 20, higher education is a post-secondary education level, including diploma, bachelor, master, specialist, and doctoral education programs. Indonesia's type of higher education is academic, professional, and vocational. The primary goal of academic education is to master specific scientific disciplines, and professional education prepares students for jobs with special skills requirements, while vocational education prepares students for jobs with specific applied skills. Indonesian education in academies, colleges, institutes or universities (Rifandi, 2013). Higher education institutions always try to improve alumni quality through more up-to-date learning programs supported by a diverse learning evaluation system. It is done to achieve the goal of establishing higher education as set out in Law No. 12 of 2012; Article 5 mentions 4 (four) higher education goals, namely:

1. To develop students' potential to become human beings who believe in and fear God Almighty and have noble, healthy, knowledgeable, competent, creative, independent, skilled, competent, and cultured characters to benefit the nation.
2. Produce graduates who master the branches of Science and Technology to fulfil national interests and increase the nation's competitiveness.
3. Production of science and innovative technologies through research focuses on and applies the values with humanities in order to support the country's development and the progress of civilization and the well-being of humanity.
4. It was realizing community service based on the reasoning that is useful in advancing the general welfare and educating the nation's life.

To achieve this goal, one of the activities carried out by universities is to evaluate learning (Alannasir, 2020). Learning evaluation according to Basically every student is required to attend lectures and follow the evaluation of the success of the student learning process as determined in the lecture plan for each course (Salam 2005: 117). The evaluation aims to determine the success of students participating in all planned educational programs. Exams as a reference material to identify and evaluate students can also be used as a reference. It is determining success criteria. Usually, the Cumulative Achievement Index (GPA) states this success. State Islamic Institute of Palopo (IAIN Palopo), formerly known as the Islamic State College of Palopo (STAIN Palopo), officially changed its status in 2014 to strive to improve the quality of its education. One of the efforts made is in evaluating learning.

METHODS

This type of research is qualitative research. The theoretical understanding of qualitative research is research that is limited to an attempt to reveal a problem, and in the state, it is so that it is only a disclosure of facts (Warsito, 1997: 10). So, the data generated in this study are not in the form of numbers, but data that are expressed symbolically in the form of written or written words, non-verbal responses, literal oral, or descriptive form (Moleong, 1995: 6). Although this study focuses on qualitative data, the researcher does not ignore quantitative data if needed, which is described in the form of expression. After that, the researcher tried to give meaning to the quantitative data.

These approaches include pedagogical, legal, and sociological approaches. The objects were academic executors and students. The academic executor in question was officially responsible for the continuity of a learning assessment in terms of providing facilities and infrastructure, as well as budget issues. The academic executor consists of Vice-Rector I, Faculty Academic Section Head, and Faculty Academic Subdivision. Ushuluddin, Adab, and Da'wah, Head of the Academic Subdivision of the Faculty of Tarbiyah and Teacher Training, Head of the Academic Subdivision of the Faculty of Economics and Islamic Business, and Head of the Sharia Faculty Academic Subdivision.

Meanwhile, the intended students are all students who have conditions to follow the learning evaluation. In this study, researchers selected 2016 graduates and 2017 academic year final semester students. The research tools used in this study were guidelines, interview guides, and documentation. The researcher, as a human instrument, is also the main instrument. The data analysis process is also performed in three continuous stages, namely data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion.

RESULTS

Implementation of Learning Evaluation Management at IAIN Palopo

Learning evaluation management at IAIN Palopo includes planning learning evaluation, organizing learning evaluation, implementing learning evaluation, and evaluating learning evaluation program. The translation is as follows:

a. Planning

Evaluation planning must be clearly and accurately formulated to be a guide and reference in determining the next steps. Through evaluation planning, all stakeholders can set behavioural goals to be achieved, prepare the required information gathering, and use the time set in current general references. Vice-Rector I, as the person in charge of academic and institutional fields that plays a significant role in determining the success of existing work programs, including learning assessment. One of Vice-Rector I 's responsibilities in evaluating learning is to prepare an annual academic calendar as a reference for activities. The learning evaluation must refer to the current academic calendar so that all activities can be organized and well planned (Rustan, 2017, Interview). Wahyuni Husain, Head of the Islamic Counseling Study Program (BPI), explained that the study program chairman's planning was as follows:

In order to fulfil its duties and responsibilities, the study program head, in terms of planning the evaluation of learning, develops a smart strategy for empowering educational staff through cooperation or cooperation, enabling lecturers to improve their profession and encouraging the involvement of all human resources in various activities that support legal programs. (Wahyuni, 2017, Interview).

The first step in planning a learning evaluation is to hold an internal meeting to discuss learning evaluation. The meeting discussed the following : (1) determining the allocation of time for activities, (2) determining learning evaluation objectives, (3) applying the collection of questions to be tested to academic staff, (3) elaborating the types of evaluations to be used. These steps are as follows:

1) Determination of Time

The first step is to determine time allocation for learning evaluation. Following are the results of an interview with one of the Heads of the Subdivision in the academic field who said: "In determining the time for each learning evaluation, especially UAS, of course, it refers to the current academic calendar but continues to pay attention to other Learning evaluation objectives can be organized to achieve learning goals. The following interview with Muhammad Guntur stated that "the purpose of learning evaluation must refer to the learning indicators given, or at least the purpose of learning evaluation must include two aspects: audience (students) and behaviour (skills)" (Guntur, 2017, Interview). Indeed, determining learning evaluation goals does not come from the predetermined aspects, namely collecting various information that will be used as evidence of developments experienced by students after having followed the learning process for a specified period. In other words, the goal of obtaining evidence will be an indication of students ' level of ability and success in achieving various learning goals after taking the learning process in a predetermined time. It also aims to measure and assess the extent to which teaching efficiency and various teaching methods were applied or implemented.aspects, particularly the completeness of the course" (Misnawati, 2017, Interview). Determining time allocation can be seen from the confirmation results of the analysis

performed on attendance and lecture journals. Based on the observations, the time allocation has been determined; each lecturer's estimated average time is different. Thus, these allocations can be detailed and re-adjusted by the course lecturers.

2) Determination of learning evaluation objectives.

Learning evaluation targets can be structured to meet learning goals. The following interview with Muhammad Guntur stated that "the purpose of learning evaluation must refer to the learning indicators given, or at least the purpose of learning evaluation must include two aspects: audience (students) and behaviour (skills)" (Guntur, 2017, Interview). Assessing learning evaluation objectives does not come from the prescribed factors, including gathering various information that will be used as proof of changes experienced by students after having followed the learning process for a specified period. In other words, the goal of obtaining evidence will be an indicator of students' level of ability and success in achieving different learning goals after completing the learning process in a predetermined time. It also aims to measure and assess the extent to which teaching productivity and different teaching methods are introduced or enforced.

3) Development of Learning evaluation activities

Each learning evaluation activity is designed to provide students with a quality learning experience where mental and physical processes occur through interactions between students, students and lecturers, environment, and other learning resources to achieve completeness. Learning. The learning experience in question will generally be realized using a varied, student-centred learning evaluation approach. Also, the learning evaluation experience must accommodate life skills training, which is essential to the students. The results of an interview with Sharia Economics study program head who said:

The following are some things that need to be considered when lecturers make learning evaluation-related developments: (1) Learning evaluation activities are designed to assist lecturers to know the extent of the learning process achieved by students. (2) The learning evaluation activity shall describe the material taught by the lecturer so that, later, students can find out the form of the material being tested in the syllabus. (Ilham, 2017, Interview).

Likewise, the results of observations made by researchers indicate that learning evaluation activities are steps that must be taken by the lecturer to encourage students to learn actively.

4) Description of the types of assessment to be used

Several types of assessments used at IAIN Palopo include those described by Alia Lestari:

The syllabus referenced the type of evaluation to be used for each learning assessment. The student achievement assessment is based on indicators already developed. Assessment, especially at UTS and UAS, is performed using tests and non-tests in the form of written (paper test) or oral, performance observations, attitude measurement, work assessment in the form of assignments, projects and products, portfolio use and self - assessment (self - assessment). Therefore, students are triggered to produce works in each lecture, so presenting papers is a way of assessment that must be done at the educational level, including in tertiary institutions. Meanwhile, evaluation is a series of activities aimed at obtaining, analyzing, and interpreting data on student learning processes and outcomes that are carried out systematically and continuously to become meaningful information in decision - making. (Alia, 2017, Interview).

Based on the results of an interview with one of the lecturers who teach a subject, it is known that IAIN Palopo lecturers pay attention to the following issues to design a proper assessment: (1) The assessment is aimed at measuring competency achievement. (2) The assessment uses the criteria reference; that is, based on what students can do after attending the lecture process and does not determine the group's position. (3) The planned system is a continuous evaluation system; it continues to maintain, in the specific context where the indicators are evaluated, the results analyzed to identify the necessary competences and identify student difficulties. (4) Evaluation results are analyzed to determine to follow - up. Follow - up is in the form of improvements to the next lecture process, a remedial program for students whose skills are below completeness, and an enrichment program for students who have fulfilled their completeness. (5) The evaluation system must adapt to the learning experience of the learning process. For example, if learning uses a field observation task approach, processes such as interview techniques and products in the form of field observation results must be evaluated (Alia, 2017, Interview).

b. Organizing

In one of the interviews, Rustan S, Vice-Rector I, who is fully responsible for managing the administrative field at IAIN Palopo, explained that:

As for learning evaluation at IAIN Palopo, of course, all components are maximized from the existing organizational structure so that the learning evaluation program runs smoothly. A well-implemented evaluation indicator is that it runs well every year. (Rustan, 2017, Interview).

Manage learning evaluation after planning the learning evaluation. As Wahyuni Husain said, learning evaluation time is Vice-Rector I's authority. The academy calendar set the learning evaluation time. However, through the Head of Study Programs, the Dean of the respective faculties coordinates distribution and scheduling at the study program level (Wahyuni, 2017, Interview). Management of learning evaluations performed at the study program level is primarily related to UAS at IAIN Palopo, including (1) Requesting and collecting evaluation questions from each lecturer who teaches the course, (2) developing a learning evaluation schedule, (3) preparing examination response sheets based on the timetable reported by the lecturer who teaches the course unless the examination is performed (Suriani, 2017, Interview).

c. Implementation

The implementation of learning evaluation activities carried out by the lecturer to measure the result of learning that has been prepared on the syllabus to aimed at improving the quality. Therefore the implementation of learning evaluation activities applies the method/strategy steps of each lecturer. However, there are general procedures that have been applied so far in study programs/faculties at IAIN Palopo, as for the implementation are as follows:

1) UTS

The requirements and implementation of the UTS are as follows:

- a) Mid-Semester Examination (UTS) is carried out independently by the lecturer concerned. Regarding the model and examination system, it is entirely up to the lecturer concerned.
- b) The lecturer who teaches courses prepares exam questions and submits exam questions in hard copy and soft copy to the Department for archiving.
- c) Lecturers act as examiners as well as examination supervisors.
- d) For lecturers who are unable to carry out supervision, they must notify the Department / Academic Section before their courses are tested.
- e) Lecturers take the exam answer sheets (unless the test is done in non-written forms, such as an oral test), attendance lists, and assessment sheets in the Academic Section.
- f) Lecturers who supervise the implementation of the UTS by paying attention to the following conditions:
 - (1) Students (exam participants) must arrive at 10 (ten) minutes before the start of the exam.
 - (2) Test takers are required to wear neat and polite clothes, namely:
 - Boys: White shirt and black trousers
 - Women: white long sleeve brackets, long black skirt, and a black headscarf.
 - (3) Examination participants are prohibited from bringing books, notes, and bags into the exam room except for open book exams.
 - (4) Test participants must bring their writing instruments.
 - (5) Test participants are not allowed to work on questions before there is permission from the lecturer/examination supervisor
 - (6) Write down personal data (name, nim, major, and others) on the exam answer sheet.
 - (7) A new exam participant is allowed to leave the room after 30 minutes of the exam and leave the answer sheet on his seat without disturbing the peace of the exam.
 - (8) An exam participant who is more than 30 minutes late is no longer allowed to take the exam. Participants who are found to be cheating may be excluded from the exam or other sanctions set.
 - (9) Students who do not attend the specified exam time are declared not to use the exam opportunities provided, and the score is considered zero.
 - (10) The lecturer enters the exam room and instructs the examinees to put their bags, books, notes, and communication tools in front of the exam room.

- (11) The lecturer checks the completeness of the exam participants, such as the student's Study Plan Card (KRS) and clothes according to the examination rules.
 - (12) On the scheduled exam start schedule, the lecturer distributes blank answer sheets and question sheets that have been provided. Correctly, for subjects related to calculation, additional blank sheets of paper were distributed, which could be used by students to assist the calculation process.
 - (13) After approximately 30 (thirty) minutes after the start of the exam, the lecturer will attend the attendance of the exam participant.
 - (14) During the exam, the lecturer supervises the ongoing process of the exam and the activities of the exam participant. If there is an exam participant who has completed the exam questions before the time provided for the exam ends, the lecturer can immediately take the answer sheet placed by the examinee on the exam table.
 - (15) For students who are unable to take the exam on a determined schedule due to illness or otherwise, it is necessary to notify the lecturer concerned in writing, enclosing evidence (information about illness from a doctor or other).
 - (16) Follow-up examinations for students who are sick and unable to attend will be determined later by the lecturer concerned. The form and system of the follow-up examinations are entirely up to the lecturer concerned
- g) The UTS score is submitted to the Department after the midterm test of the subject has been tested, or based on the final time, the midterm examination score is submitted by the Faculty (Misnawati, 2017, Documentation).

2) UAS

The requirements and implementation of the UAS are as follows:

- a) To be able to take UAS, students are required to attend lectures 100% with an absence tolerance of 25% of the total face-to-face (Draft Team, 2016: 18).
- b) Middle Semester Examination (UAS) is carried out independently by the lecturer concerned. Regarding the model and examination system, it is entirely up to the lecturer concerned.
- c) The lecturer who teaches courses prepares exam questions and submits exam questions in hard copy and soft copy to the Department for archiving.
- d) Lecturers act as examiners as well as examination supervisors.
- e) For lecturers who are unable to carry out supervision, they must notify the Department / Academic Section before the course is tested.
- f) Lecturers take the exam answer sheets (except when the test is conducted in non-written forms, such as an oral test), attendance lists, and assessment sheets in the academic section.
- g) Lecturers who supervise the implementation of the UAS by paying attention to the following conditions:
 - (1) Students (exam participants) must arrive at 10 (ten) minutes before the start of the exam.
 - (2) Examination participants are required to wear:
 - Boys: White shirt and black trousers
 - Women: white long sleeve brackets, long black skirt, and a black headscarf.
 - (3) Examination participants are prohibited from bringing books, notes, and bags into the exam room except for open book exams.
 - (4) Test participants must bring their writing instruments.
 - (5) Test participants are not allowed to work on questions before there is permission from the lecturer/examination supervisor.
 - (6) Write down personal data (name, NIM, study program, and class) on the exam answer sheet.
 - (7) A new exam participant is allowed to leave the room after 30 minutes of the exam and leave the answer sheet on his seat without disturbing the peace of the exam.
 - (8) An exam participant who is more than 30 minutes late is no longer allowed to take the exam. Participants who are found to be cheating may be excluded from the exam or other sanctions set.
 - (9) Students who do not attend the specified exam time are declared not to use the exam opportunities provided, and the score is considered zero.

- (10) The lecturer enters the exam room and instructs the examinees to put their bags, books, notes, and communication tools in front of the exam room.
 - (11) The lecturer checks the completeness of the exam participants, such as the student's Study Plan Card (KRS) and clothes according to the examination rules.
 - (12) On the scheduled exam start schedule, the lecturer distributes blank answer sheets and question sheets that have been provided. Correctly, for subjects related to calculation, additional blank sheets of paper were distributed, which could be used by students to assist the calculation process.
 - (13) After approximately 30 (thirty) minutes after the start of the exam, the lecturer will attend the attendance of the exam participant.
 - (14) During the exam, the lecturer supervises the process of taking place and the activities of the exam participants.
 - (15) If there is an exam participant who has finished the exam questions before the time provided for the exam ends, the lecturer can immediately take the answer sheet that the exam participant puts on the exam table.
 - (16) Students who are unable to take the exam on a specified schedule due to illness or otherwise, should notify the lecturer concerned in writing, enclosing evidence (information about illness from a doctor or other).
 - (17) Follow-up examinations for students who are sick and unable to attend will be determined later by the lecturer concerned. The form and system of the follow-up examinations are entirely up to the lecturer concerned
- h) The UAS scores are submitted to the Department after the midterm test of the subject has been tested or based on the final time of submission of the midterm exam scores determined by the Faculty (Suriani, 2017, Documentation).

3) Comprehensive

The Comprehensive Examination, which was conducted at IAIN Palopo, was conducted using an oral test, which was conducted by interview. The requirements and implementation of the comprehensive exam are as follows:

- a) Comprehensive examinations can be carried out if students have passed all theoretical and practical courses as evidenced by the transcript of temporary grades signed by the Dean of the Faculty;
- b) Students are registered as active students, not students who are on academic leave, and
- c) Students register to take a comprehensive exam by attaching transcripts of passing grades, a statement of passing the thesis proposal seminar.
- d) Comprehensive examinations performed out by the committee, determined by the Dean with the determination of the decree for each faculty.
- e) Acting as examiners are lecturers who have been stipulated in the committee decree.
- f) Students (test-takers) must arrive at 10 (ten) minutes before the exam starts.
- g) Test takers are required to wear neat and polite clothes, namely:
 - (1) Male: white shirt and black trousers
 - (2) Women: white long sleeve brackets, long black skirt, and blackhead scarf.
- h) For students who are unable to take the exam on a specified schedule due to illness or otherwise, please notify the committee in writing, enclosing evidence (information about illness from a doctor or other).
- i) Follow-up exams for students who are sick and unable to attend will be determined later by the examining lecturer. The form and system of follow-up examinations entirely left to the lecturer who teaches the course or the lecturer who gives the course.
- j) Comprehensive Exam scores are submitted to the study program after the exam for the relevant course has been tested, or based on the final time, the score has been determined by the Faculty (Wahyuni, 2017, Documentation).

Lecturers in providing assessments at IAIN Palopo, especially on learning evaluation (UTS and UAS), refer to the standardization as set out in the 2016 academic guidelines. Assessment is a process and activity to determine the achievement of student competencies during and after participating in the learning process. Assessment is carried out in an integrated manner to reveal all aspects of student abilities both in cognitive, affective, normative, and psychomotor aspects. Learning assessment includes

an assessment of the learning process and the assessment of learning outcomes. The translation is as follows:

1) Process assessment

Learning process assessment is intended to reveal the student's ability to participate in the learning process. Assessment can be done by observation, anecdotal or other means. Process assessment is performed both individually and in groups during the learning process. The standards used in the evaluation process can be seen from active student discipline, courtesy to lecturers and other participants, mentally and socially in the learning process, as well as high - level learning activities, great learning enthusiasm, and self - confidence with daily testing and program performed with the given written test (Guntur, 2017, Interview). Determining minimum completeness provides a three-domain assessment, namely:

- a) Cognitive domain, cognitive assessment is carried out with a written test. Programmed daily tests. If in the daily test, the student has not reached the completeness of learning, a remedial program is held. Programmed daily tests are intended to improve student performance and learning outcomes in a sustainable manner.
- b) Psychomotor assessment is being considered based on the material and methods used, for example, the discussion method, and the assessment aspects include attention to lessons, the accuracy of giving examples, the ability to express opinions and the ability to question and answer, as well as the form of performance and day-to-day work, such as reciting and writing verses of the Koran, and many more.
- c) Affective domain, the criteria being assessed include attendance, politeness, diligence, discipline, friendliness, accuracy in collecting assignments, participation in learning, attention to lessons (Alia, 2017, Interview).

2) Assessment of results

The learning process is said to be successful if there is a positive behaviour change in all or most of the students. In carrying out the results, assessment is carried out at the middle and end of the semester by holding an assessment activity in order to get a complete and comprehensive picture of student learning completeness in a particular time unit. In assessing these results, the criteria are as follows:

- a) Method of Assessment: Assessment can be done using tests and non-tests.
- b) Form of Assessment: Assessment of learning outcomes can take the form of tests, projects, products, performance, portfolios, and observations.
- c) Assessment Time: Assessment of learning outcomes is carried out in the span of mid-semester and end of the semester.
- d) Evaluation Norms
 - (1) Every student is obliged and entitled to participate in the learning activities of all courses listed in KRS.
 - (2) Students are required to attend a minimum of 75% of all learning activities in order to be declared entitled to take exams and to get the final learning result score.
 - (3) The minimum limit for lecturer attendance must meet a minimum of 14 meetings/face-to-face meetings or 16 meetings, including midterm and final semester exams.
 - (4) Students are only entitled to take exams for the courses listed in the current semester KRS.
 - (5) The procedure for administering the examination and assessment guidelines is regulated in a separate manual prepared by the faculty. The assessment of learning outcomes at the end of the semester is carried out by the teaching lecturer based on the study contract listed in the KRS of each course, which includes, among other things, midterm exam scores, final exams, assignments, attendance, and other activities.
 - (6) If there is a delay at the end of the semester learning result scores from the lecturer, the Kajur / Head of Study Program has the right to ask the lecturer concerned in writing. If within the specified time limit, the value has not been received, the Kajur / Head of Study Program has the right to hold a follow-up exam and then give the student a grade.
 - (7) Students who do not have a midterm and final semester test scores are not entitled to the final study result scores.

- (8) Students have the right to convey orally or in writing to a lecturer, department/study program, or faculty evaluation and objections about the learning process and the results of the assessment.
- (9) The value of learning outcomes in the form of alphabet characters converted from graded numbers.

e) Change in Value

- (1) Students may submit value dissatisfaction to the Head of the Faculty Administration Section concerned by filling in the form up to a maximum of 7 (seven) days after the score has been announced.
- (2) The value may change if:
 - The material complained of is correct, the value changes up according to the correction of the teaching lecturer;
 - The material being complained of is not correct/making it up; the lecturer has the right to lower the score at least 1 (one) interval.
- (3) Changes in value at the initiative of a lecturer can only be done if it has the approval of the Head of Department / Study Program with acceptable reasons.

f) Determination of Study Results

- (1) Assessment is part of the learning process, which functions to evaluate the progress and abilities of students in achieving competencies, as stated by the Achievement Index (IP).
- (2) Achievement Index is determined at the end of each semester, which is called Semester IP, while the IP of all learning outcomes that have been taken is called the Grade Point Average (GPA).

g) Predicate of Graduation

Undergraduate students who are declared graduated receive the predicate of graduation with the following conditions:

(1) Predicate with Praise

To achieve the predicate with Praise

- Minimum GPA of 3.51.
 - The maximum number of programmed semesters (10 semesters) has been undertaken.
 - If a student with a GPA of 3.51 and above but the study period exceeds ten semesters, then the graduation predicate is Very Satisfactory.
- (2) Predicate Very Satisfactory if: GPA 3.01 - 3.50
 - (3) Satisfactory predicate if: GPA 2.76 - 3.00
 - (4) Sufficient predicate if: GPA $\leq$ 2.75

h) Rating System

- (1) In the assessment system, students are given a grade according to student rights with the following components:
 - UAS (25% - 40%)
 - UTS (20% - 30%)
 - Duty (15% - 30%)
 - Participation (0 - 15%)
 - Attendance (0-15%)
 (The total percentage of all components must be 100%) *) except for courses with particular characteristics.
- (2) To be able to take UAS, students must attend lectures 100% with a non-attendance tolerance of 25% of the face-to-face number.
- (3) Lecturers enter the class 14 times face to face for 2 or 3 credits, 28 times face to face for 4 or 6 credits, and the rest applies multiples.
- (4) There is no follow-up exam in any form after the assessment period ends.

d. Evaluation of the Teaching Evaluation Program

The institution's evaluation of the learning evaluation program is a service provided by the institution to help lecturers become more competent/skilled in carrying out their duties on time demands. Supervising and evaluating technical implementation issues and developing learning evaluations in the form of program enhancements to achieve the goals of the topic. Quality Assurance Institute (LPM) always tries to audit the study program's sustainability course, including learning evaluation. It is done to meet the quality aspect needs of each existing study program because learning

evaluation is part of the factors affecting quality improvement (Madehang, 2017, Interview). As an institution evaluating academic activities (PMA No. 6, 2017), LPM currently only audits the results of existing evaluations while the faculty and study program conduct the evaluation.

Learning Evaluation Management Constraints at IAIN Palopo

Every program, including a learning evaluation program, certainly has obstacles in its implementation. Likewise, the evaluation of learning programs at IAIN Palopo has various kinds of obstacles in its implementation, as for the constraints of the learning evaluation program, including:

a. Planning

Learning evaluation planning is very influential in the success or failure of the program. The obstacles faced in planning the learning evaluation at IAIN Palopo, which are prominent, are that every learning evaluation is carried out, there are courses whose material has not been completed. The condition thus hindering existing planning. Misnawati states that the main obstacle in planning the evaluation of learning, generally, was the course did not meet the requirements to be evaluated or had not reached the middle of the material. At the same time, on the comprehensive exam, on average, there are problems for the students concerned who have not received scores from all the existing courses (Misnawati, 2017, Interview). From the interview, it was evident that the accuracy in providing the subject matter, the completeness of the material affects the learning evaluation planning.

b. Organizing

Organizing is part of a management process which can not be ruled out. It needs coordination in order to improve the planning activities which have already planning to be carried out. There are several obstacles to the learning evaluation activities at IAIN Palopo in coordination. According to Ilham, who argues that the constraints of the learning assessment were due to the problem of incomplete teaching materials, the facility was inadequate and did not follow the previous plan. (Ilham, 2017, Interview).

c. Implementation

Based on the results of research on the constraints of carrying out the learning evaluation, it was observed that the dominant factor was the frequency of student cheating, as Wahyuni Husain stated, the obstacles faced in the learning evaluation process were that there were still many students who cheated in the form of cheating, open books and cooperated on q Fraud. It is complicated to avoid as examination schedules often collide so that lecturers have to send replacements to oversee the implementation of learning evaluation (UTS and UAS), in addition to the fact that the obstacles in the comprehensive examination are wrong, the only one is that students do not re-examine past lessons before entering the examination room. Muh, Muh. Ruslan added that student cheating often occurs. Even this was deemed reasonable by students, so some unscrupulous students repeatedly cheated. Learning evaluation activities, especially at UTS and UAS, are cheated by open books, cell phone browsing, or even working with close friends. It usually occurs when the teacher is not strictly monitoring the learning evaluation course, and it often happens when the supervision is performed by a replacement lecturer/supervisor (Ruslan, 2017, Interview).

Based on these interviews and researchers' observations, it was found that fraudulent learning assessment stems from a lack of assertiveness in supervision, the previous school's culture, and suggestions allowing academic fraud to take place, the researcher believes that this fraud can be overcome by raising supervisory standards for evaluation. The assessment is monitored explicitly by the lecturer, who conducts the course.

d. Program Evaluation

A program's success is not enough to evaluate student learning outcomes as a product of a learning evaluation process. Product quality is inseparable from process quality itself. Evaluation of programs designed and implemented should include evaluations of 1) program design, which includes the competencies to be achieved, selected strategy and program content, 2) program implementation, and 3) program outcomes. In evaluating program results, it is not sufficiently limited to short-term results or outputs, but should also reach a program outcome. To date, the evaluation of the learning evaluation program at IAIN Palopo has been uncertain. However, it still runs as it should, this can be seen from changes made to certain aspects of the learning evaluation program, including supervision, and the absence of a learning evaluation committee. (UTS, UAS). In one of the interviews, Muhammad Hajarul Aswad A explained that one of the obstacles in IAIN Palopo's learning evaluation was that it was

not well planned so that the program evaluation considered necessary to be updated was not completely changed. As for changes usually occur only in individual faculties, so other faculties apply the same thing if deemed suitable to be followed (Aswad, 2017, Interview). EOLBREAK Based on the interview, it can be seen that the main obstacle in evaluating the learning evaluation program is related to budget availability in order to adjust the existing budget allocations to implement the program evaluation. The government has routinely implemented a budget-saving policy in recent years. This budget-saving is a budget cut by some percentage of government ministries/agencies budget. Budget savings are intended as an efficiency effort and a large part of the government's priority programs/activities.

DISCUSSION

A good program is a program that has well-designed planning, organization, implementation, and evaluation, including learning evaluation. IAIN Palopo evaluations of planning, organizing, implementing, and evaluating programs are carried out by stakeholders following their respective duties and functions. In planning the learning evaluation, the Head of the Study Program and Academic Subdivision Head has a crucial role to play in promoting the program's sustainability. Similarly, lecturers teaching courses are at the heart of the program's operation, the completeness of the learning courses, and the depositing/reporting of questions, which are, of course, essential elements for learning assessment. Similarly, cleaning services that help readiness to use the room and other helpers' needs are one factor that can not be excluded. Thus learning evaluation can be performed as planned. The supervisory discipline depends on how lecturers evaluate existing learning. Regarding the evaluation of the learning evaluation program at IAIN Palopo, it is conducted periodically without a specified time so that the evaluation can be carried out at any time, depending on the needs and essential aspects to be assessed.

Inhibiting Factors for Learning Evaluation at IAIN Palopo

Education services from a technical-administrative point of view are generally not yet fully effective and efficient, for this reason, management of educational services is needed for the realization of quality education in order to build trustworthy, efficient, productive and accountable education services through good governance (good governance) based on educational institutions. Information technology. Although it is also felt that it is still low and unable to meet the needs of students and development, which is mainly due to the lack of support:

- a. Lack of and unequal teaching and education personnel, both in quantity and quality;
- b. Inadequate availability of learning facilities and supporting infrastructure, including educational teaching equipment. The very rapid development of the number of students, in the last five years, requires the addition and maintenance of facilities and infrastructure for lectures, learning media, and other things that can support the learning process;
- c. The not yet functioning quality control system and quality assurance of education, development of information technology-based management information systems in academic services, namely, academic information systems, digital libraries, online journals, and other information systems that support the learning process; and
- d. The unavailability of operational costs required for the implementation of quality teaching and learning processes.

Due to the lack of standard education services in terms of input, process, and output, the system of quality control and education quality assurance has not worked well. The education quality evaluation system is also considered imperfect. Several factors are the main obstacles to implementing IAIN Palopo 's learning evaluation. Based on the results of the interview, the limiting factors were: (a) some unscrupulous lecturers did not finish the lecture on time; (b) lack of adequate advice and infrastructure; (c) fraud in the implementation of learning evaluations; (d) budgetary savings policies resulting in program evaluation failure

CONCLUSION

IAIN Palopo 's Learning Evaluation Management includes planning, organizing, implementing, and evaluating programs. At the planning stage, the academic side prepares every need to be used in the evaluation of learning, then organizes scheduling arrangements by referring to the existing academic

calendar and arranging the place for lectures. At the same time, at the implementation stage of the learning evaluation, especially at UTS and UAS, supervisors or lecturers are directly supervised. As for evaluating learning programs carried out by agencies as appropriate, considering essential issues that will be evaluated. IAIN Palopo 's learning evaluation management constraints include; incomplete multiple course materials (UTS and UAS) to affect planning, besides some students have not received scores in the previous semester (comprehensive examinations), some lecturers are late in entering the test questions in the organizational aspect. We tested the material but did not provide information to the study program/faculty, other than that the facilities aspect was less influential in organizing the learning evaluation. Obstacles in the implementation aspect of learning evaluation are the lack of student preparation in facing exams, student fraud committed during the exam. The problem with program evaluation is that there is no set time for program evaluation.

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